

EFFECTS OF HEAVY METALS ON SOILS.**Jobborov Bakhrom Turgunovich**

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Annotation: In this article, the soils of the regions polluted with heavy metals in the Tashkent region were analyzed. It also provides information on waste reduction and soil pollution studies, analysis, and reduction of harmful chemicals.

Keywords: Heavy metals, soil, industry, population, food, production, metallurgy, fertility, waste.

The contribution of metallurgical enterprises plays an important role in increasing the industrial economy of our country. Because we can say that it is one of the sources that serve to increase the economic efficiency of the country. Today, the study of the ecological condition of the industrialized areas, including the study of the physical, chemical, mechanical, agrochemical and biological properties of the soil, is considered one of the urgent issues by scientific researchers. The purpose of this is to control soil fertility indicators, to identify ecologically polluted soils and to develop practical recommendations on the effective use of man-made damaged, i.e., polluted areas, to increase the country's economic efficiency and provide clean food products [1, 2, 3, 4]. As a result of the activity of the Metallurgical Combine of Uzbekistan, scientific studies were conducted on the changes in the ecological conditions of soils during the scientific research. According to the obtained results, ferrous and non-ferrous metallurgical enterprises are in the first place among all industrial sectors in terms of the release of harmful substances. In particular, they significantly affect soils. Some scientists determined the concentration of heavy metals Cu, Zn, Ni, Co, Fe, Mn, Cr, Pb, Hg, Cd, Ba, Sr and Sc in the soil and bottom sediments in the regions of the north of Western Siberia under the influence of oil and gas enterprises. It was found that the concentration of heavy metals in peat soils is 3-4 times higher than in the horizons of clay soils [5]. It may also lead to man-made contamination of soils and their unusability in some cases. Studying the ecological condition of the soil of our industrialized regions today, reducing its harmful effects is one of the urgent issues. The most significant impact of the enterprises of the metallurgical complex on the soil is the landfills formed in the course of production activities. Metallurgical enterprises pollute the soil with heavy metals, sulfur, phosphorus and fluorine compounds, as well as

compounds of the class of aromatic hydrocarbons. Accumulation of heavy metals in soils is increasing rapidly due to anthropogenic (industrial) activities. Heavy metals in soil are non-biodegradable and persist in the environment, eventually passing through plants into the food chain and eventually entering and accumulating in the human body. This situation has a negative impact on people's health. Phytoremediation is an environmentally friendly approach to treating heavy metal-contaminated soils and has been found to be economically viable [6]. Soil pollution is observed as a result of the increase in industrial and production sectors due to the increase in population. Industry is considered the most objective indicator as a source of information about the geo ecological condition of the soil, mainly industrialized areas. Because the main streams of most pollutants are emitted from industrial networks. Also, in industrialized areas, heavy metals accumulate in the soil under the influence of waste from industries. This changes the ecological condition of the soil and reduces its productivity.

Some industries of Tashkent region

1- picture

According to the analysis of the data obtained during the scientific research, it was found necessary to divide these areas into three groups, depending on the level of soil pollution and ecological condition of the industrialized area. Groups of this tune, i.e. the first one is the red zone, Angren thermal power station, Almalyk mining metallurgical combine JSCs were allocated to it. The second is the yellow areas, which include Angren thermal power station, Ammofos-Maxam JSC, Bekabadsement JSC and Metallurgical Combine of Uzbekistan JSC. And the third one is the soils scattered around the Angren oil base. During the long-term

activity of Ammafos-Maxam JSC, located in Bekabad district, the waste was collected for processing around the area. Soils are polluted as a result of the release of these wastes into the environment as a result of climatic factors. In addition, the waste present in these landfills causes pollution of the atmosphere and hydrosphere. It can be seen that due to the large amount of polluting chemicals entering the soil, the self-cleaning ability of the soil was observed at a low level. Heavy metals deposited in soils have variable valency, which determines their ability to undergo chemical and biochemical changes and, therefore, their ability to migrate over long distances. This is one of the sources of man-made soil pollution. In addition, it was found that the concentration of heavy metals in vegetable crops grown in polluted soils was higher than the same crops grown in a relatively clean area.

Conclusion: A scientific study was conducted on the ecological condition of soils scattered in some industrialized areas of Tashkent region. We can directly say that heavy metals and some wastes in the form of dust have a high negative impact on the environment, especially on the soil. This directly determines the importance of conducting scientific research on these man-made polluted areas. It is also necessary to develop practical recommendations for the effective use of such man-made polluted areas, the wider introduction of technologies for the processing of waste from industrial sectors, and the reduction of the amount of waste. The use of these measures in industrialized areas will allow them to significantly improve the ecological condition of the environment in the adjacent areas.

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